

ON THE PATH OF MATURATION OF THE YOUNGER GENERATION

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In the recent period, extensive reforms have been carried out in our country, covering all areas, and these works are continuing in a new phase and in a more consistent way in the current period. Whether it is a state management structure or health, sports, education — let it give a positive result in all aspects. It should be noted that in the era of globalization today, in the conditions of the height of the ideological struggle in the world, we must always live alert, sensitive and spiritually awake, understand the meaning and meaning of our work towards preserving and strengthening the atmosphere of interethnic harmony, mutual kindness and harmony in our country, which is our greatest wealth. It is an urgent task to educate the growing younger generation in the spirit of patriotism and nationalism. This requires increased attention to education and upbringing in the family and educational institutions. A number of legislative acts aimed at the solution of this sphere are signed by our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev and decrees, resolutions and orders are adopted. These serve to mature a harmonious generation in our country, spiritually mature, with a keen worldview, an independent thinker, a strong faith, whose political and spiritual level fully meets the requirements of the current era. Human essence is manifested in the confluence of substance and spirituality. Each shahs, each social group or category, each elat, nation and region rings are created by their nature. After all, an approach to the issues of spirituality and its realization taking into account the rational, concrete conditions is important in opening up new ways to educate a perfect person. Bedil said that if the architect does not correctly lay the original brick, the head of the

building, even if it reaches the stars, it will remain Crooked. Therefore, the place of a person in society is determined not by his material assets, but by his high spiritual image. Consequently, spirituality is a bridge connecting ancestors to generations, history to today, and today to the future. He embodies the unique qualities, a set of values and traditions that are inherited from our ancestors, as well as the historical and social experience they have accumulated and all views."The Union of youth of Uzbekistan," the head of State Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in a speech at the IV Congress of Kamolot, " respect for the heritage of our great ancestors, which has made an invaluable contribution to the development of World Culture, the formation of a sense of being worthy of it, the content aimed at deep study and broad promotion of this invaluable wealth, it would be light on the light to take the initiative in the implementation of impressive projects."Indeed, our world — famous ancestors-great statesmen, sarkarda Amir Temur, Babur Mirzo, Mirzo Ulugbek, Jaloliddin Manguberdi-were not only role models in the chapter of Valor, Justice, Humanity, science, but also paid special attention to the upbringing of their soldiers, future defenders of el-yurt. Our great thinker ancestors, who made an invaluable, significant contribution to the civilization of mankind and its bright future, such as Horazmiy, Beruniy, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Farabi, Alisher Navoi, Furqat, and Imam Buhari, Bahauddin Naqshband, Yassawi, who dong the universe in the science of religion, taught the youth spiritual and physical perfection.Among the Thinker enlighteners who lived in our recent past, Abdullah Qadiri, Abdullah Avlani, Abdurauf Fitrat, Chulpan, Mahmoud Behbudiy, The works of Uthman Nazareth and many of our great fathers are closely related to the life and upbringing of young people. But, in the time of the former saloans, our Ring of invaluable cultural and spiritual heritage of our great ancestors was presented to the minds of our youth with a special interpretation.Due to independence and on the basis of the righteous policy of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, physical education

and sports, a means of forming the gene pool of our nation and educating a harmonious generation, are increasingly becoming the "strategic weapon" of the ideology of national independence. Recently, on August 10, 2017, the decision adopted by the head of State "on the wide involvement of athletes from Uzbekistan with high results in prestigious international sports competitions in public and sports and the encouragement of athletes and their trainers" was adopted by the head of state to ensure the spiritual and physical maturation of the perfect generation in our country qilmoqda. Ma spiritual-cultural, spiritual-moral sensations and human values begin to form, first of all, from childhood. Children from early infancy try to learn from their parents, grandparents and other family members, depending on their behavior, manners, treatment relationships, family customs, painting, udum and traditions. And the only source that shapes the spirituality of the perfect generation is upbringing. The source that shapes enlightenment and knowledge is education, lessons. Consequently, it is advisable to say that it is not "education and upbringing", but, on the contrary, "upbringing and education". The role of works of art in the harmonious education of a person is great. That is why, as our president noted, along with mastering the latest achievements in the field of a-hborot-communication, special attention will be paid to increasing the interest of young people in reading books, making them friends with books, further increasing the level of reading of the population. For this, first of all, it is important that we pay special attention to the placement of the most representative samples of our national literature and world literature on social networks and their widespread promotion. Development of the system of printing and distribution of Book products "of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated January 12, 2017, the decree" on the establishment of a commission for the promotion and promotion of book reading and book culture" took the role and role of Book Culture in the spiritual life of society to another new level. Today, the spiritual worldview of some of our youth under the influence of "mass culture" is

becoming more and more fundamental. The question arises as to what measures should be taken in the fight against it. To find a solution, it is necessary to take into account the factors that, in our opinion, affect the educational system. Among them, among the most important in our opinion are the following:—to strengthen the independence of ideological work, to raise our country in every possible way and to move forward towards a bright and free life;-a perfect person who, along with such high concepts as peace of the land, prosperity of the motherland and well-being of the ring, forms the, to raise them to a new level;—to educate young people in the spirit of love for the motherland, devotion to our rich history, the sacred religion of our ancestors, first of all, the formation of ideological immunity in their hearts and minds;- to avoid the formation of a gap in their spiritual world, a healthy lifestyle in their hearts and minds, respect for, it's like shaping all-around and real perceptions of his brutal games.Our ring, in the first goal, is the urgent task of today to protect young people from ideological and ideological prejudices aimed at removing the spiritual world from the trail, directed against living as a free person.

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